

Rheumatoid Arthritis: Etiology and Cure

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ABSTRACT

Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is a chronic autoimmune disorder affecting millions globally, commonly attributed to biological, environmental, and genetic factors or their combination. Despite extensive research and various medical interventions, a definitive cure remains elusive, leaving many patients with ongoing pain, disability, and emotional challenges. Conventional treatments often focus on symptom management and may not address potential spiritual or karmic dimensions of the disease. This study explores Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu's perspective on RA as a karmic illness and presents four detailed case studies of patients who achieved full recovery through the application of Three or Four Golden Buddhist Practices. These findings suggest that, when viewed through a karmic lens, RA may be reversible through dedicated spiritual cultivation and karmic purification.

Keywords: Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door; Golden Buddhist Practices; Karma; Spirits; Rheumatoid Arthritis; Recovery

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) is a chronic, systemic autoimmune disease characterized by persistent joint inflammation, progressive cartilage and bone damage, and eventual joint deformity, causing a high incidence and disability rate, which seriously endangers human health [1]. It affects approximately 1% of the global population and disproportionately impacts women of reproductive age [2,3]. Clinically, RA presents with joint pain, stiffness, swelling, and systemic symptoms such as fatigue, anemia, and loss of function. Modern medicine has developed various pharmacologic treatments, such as disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs, biologics, and corticosteroids [3]. These therapies focus primarily on symptom management and disease control, rather than cure. For many patients, remission remains elusive, and side effects from long-term medication can be severe [4].

Despite extensive research, the precise etiology of RA remains elusive. It is often characterized as a

multifactorial disease, with contributing factors including genetic predisposition, environmental exposures, infections, and hormonal influences [1,5,6]. However, these factors frequently fail to fully account for disease onset or progression. Consequently, no curative treatment has been developed based on these findings. Similar to other chronic conditions [7], the absence of a singular root cause and effective curative solutions has led to RA being classified as an intractable, lifelong condition.

In contrast to the biomedical paradigm, alternative perspectives, particularly those grounded in Buddhist karmic principles, provide a distinct understanding of chronic illness. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, founded by Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu, considers an autoimmune condition a karmic disease [7]. Negative karma, stemming from harmful actions such as killing, verbal misconduct, or unresolved spiritual debts, is believed to contribute to its onset.

Our prior report suggests that karmic diseases may be reversible [7,8]. In this study, we analyze four detailed case reports of individuals with chronic, treatment-resistant RA who experienced significant recovery through the application of the Three or Four Golden Buddhist Practices of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. Through these cases, we aim to elucidate RA's karmic origins and propose a novel healing approach for those affected.

Underlying Mechanisms & Solutions

In the scientific community, as with many other chronic diseases such as epilepsy [9], and depression [10], the true causes of RA remain unidentified. Consequently, RA is widely believed to result from a combination of multiple factors, such as biological, environmental, and genetic factors [11,12]. Without a clear understanding of the root cause, a definitive cure remains elusive, leaving these diseases classified as 'chronic.'

Our previous studies have shown that RA is not necessarily a chronic condition. The patient can fully recover from it via Buddhism [8]. This finding aligns with Master Lu's enlightenment that RA is a karmic disease, which can be cured by eliminating karma by reciting Little Houses in batches of seven sheets, without interruption [8]. The following are 12 Dharma dialogues in which Master Lu explains arthritis in great detail and provides solutions for its healing.

Q&A 1. Speaking Too Much Ill of Others and Being Overly Talkative Lead to Painful Karmic Retribution—Arthritis as Immediate retribution [13]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on July 26, 2015)

Caller: Master, how are you? I miss you so much. Please criticize me. My cultivation has been terrible.

Master: If your cultivation has not been good, then cultivate properly from now on.

Caller: Master, can I recite the *Ru Yi Bao Lun Wang Tuo Luo Ni* (如意宝轮王陀罗尼) now?

Master: That depends. If you have accumulated enough merits and virtues, then yes, you can recite it. Once you do, things will become very auspicious.

Caller: Oh. Both of my hands have RA, and it is killing me with pain. Master, could you help me check it? I have been trying to call your Totem Reading program but cannot get through.

Master: You need to recite Buddhist scriptures diligently. With someone like you, such a bad mouth, do I even need to explain?! You have created too much negative karma through speech, so now you are facing karmic retribution in this life: "It is killing me with pain". Good that you are aware of it now. Your mouth has been far too vicious, sowing discord, speaking harshly, scolding others... you have done it all. Do I need to say more? You must truly change these bad habits.

Caller: I now realize it too. I talk way too much.

Master: Every time you open your mouth, it triggers karmic consequences. Every word may potentially create negative karma. Who told you to speak recklessly?

Caller: Master, please discipline me. Sometimes I just cannot restrain myself, I always get angry.

Master: First, how many Little Houses do you recite each day?

Caller: At least two per day.

Master: Second, do you read *Buddhism in Plain Terms* (《白话佛法》)? Be honest.

Caller: I read it every evening.

Master: One chapter each time?

Caller: Yes.

Master: Keep it up.

Caller: I really know I have been wrong. I keep getting angry and exploding. Why can't I seem to control it?

Master: Being unable to control it, in worldly terms, is called lacking self-discipline; in Buddhist terms, it means you lack a spiritual level.

Caller: Master, please criticize me, tell me off.

Master: I am not criticizing you. I do not have time. Just practice Buddhism hard. That is all. If there is nothing else, let others have a chance to call in. Be good and recite scriptures diligently. Be persistent. For this kind of pain, you need to persist. Also, soak your feet. Foot soaks can help improve the condition. If the blood circulation improves, the pain will ease.

Caller: A fellow practitioner told me that reciting the *Ru Yi Bao Lun Wang Tuo Luo Ni* while praying to Bodhisattva for better blood and meridian circulation helps. Can I do that?

Master: You can.

Caller: These past few days, this hand has been killing me with pain. I know it is because of my bad mouth. I talk too much.

Master: Do you still need to say it? You already know your speech is bad, and you are still talking? That is called “stubborn to the death, refusing to repent.” Seriously! You are in this much pain, and you are still talking? Will you die if you do not talk? I ask you.

Caller: I repent.

Master: Really hopeless. So many women just cannot keep their mouths shut, “blah, blah, blah” all day long...

Caller: Yes, I am exactly like that.

Master: You still think you have a reason? Sigh. Alright then, practice hard.

Caller: Thank you, Master!

Q&A 2. Totem Reading on RA [14]

(This dialogue took place at the Dharma Conference in Singapore on April 23, 2016)

Inquirer: Hello, Master! I was born in 1972, the Year of the Rat. I would like to ask Master to check my health. I have RA.

Master: Not only are the joints in your legs in bad condition, but even your entire spine and the bones in your lower back have problems.

Inquirer: That is right.

Master: You need to be especially careful, particularly with your diet. Right now, I see a row of spirits of living creatures, like shrimp and fish, moving along your spine. You must have eaten a lot of live creatures when you were young.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: From now on, recite the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* (往生咒) 49 times daily.

Inquirer: Okay.

Master: Also, be cautious! Your lungs are not in great condition either. You tend to cough frequently. When the weather changes, you find it hard to breathe.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: Oh, and there’s a child spirit on you. I am not sure if it is your mother’s or yours. It is jumping around. It is causing your bone problems and often makes your muscles cramp at night.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: Be careful. Your left leg is showing signs of atrophy.

Inquirer: Yes, my left joint feels very uncomfortable and painful.

Master: There is nothing else major.

Inquirer: My left hand also often cannot open up.

Master: That is not a big issue. The spirits are mainly on your spine; there is no spirit on your hand. You need to exercise more, and stretch your hand regularly, like doing morning calisthenics. Also, be more broad-minded. Your mindset is too narrow, and you get stuck in your thoughts.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: Are you married?

Inquirer: No.

Master: You need to be extra careful. Your romantic luck is very complicated. You might need to go through at least two relationships before getting married. You have already been in one, and it did not work out.

Inquirer: Yes. Master, may I ask how many Little Houses I need to recite, and how many fish should I release?

Master: You need to recite a total of 280 Little Houses, and release 3,500 fish. Do not be fooled by your thick hair. It is falling out badly.

Inquirer: Yes.

Master: Also, wash your feet more often, you do not wash them enough.

Q&A 3. Knee Joint Issues: Many Ant Spirits Are Crawling on Knee Joint [15]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on July 19, 2014)

Caller: Hello, Master! I was born in 1963, the Year of the Rabbit. I would like to ask about my health. Are there any spirits on my body?

Master: Listen carefully. Yes, there are many spirits in your body.

Caller: Where are they?

Master: On your chest. That is why you often feel tightness, discomfort, or even chest pain. Understand?

Caller: Yes. Also, my left foot—

Master: Not your foot, it is your leg.

Caller: Yes, the left leg.

Master: The joint in your left leg is not good. In the area on the upper thigh of your left leg, there are many small ant spirits crawling all over it.

Caller: Ah!

Master: You are in trouble.

Caller: What?

Master: Ants. I saw them on the totem, they are ants.

Caller: Oh, what should I do?

Master: Have you ever used hot water to scald ants in the past?

Caller: I am not sure. Maybe I have.

Master: Recite 1,000 times of the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* as soon as possible.

Q&A 4. RA: Recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* Often and Visualize the Bodhisattva Frequently [16]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Nov 10, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! My mom suddenly developed RA two years ago. What should she do?

Master: First, does your mom believe in Buddhism?

Caller: Yes, a fellow Buddhist practitioner introduced her, and she then introduced it to me. She asked me to watch the videos, and I believed right away. We both started reciting Buddhist scriptures, but my dad still does not believe it.

Master: First, your mom should quickly start reciting the *Great Compassion Mantra* (大悲咒). While reciting, she should pat the painful parts of her feet. At the same time, she should visualize Guan Yin Bodhisattva's light descending from above her head and enveloping her whole body.

Caller: Okay, thank you, Master.

Q&A 5. RA: Soak Feet in Warm Water with Liquor [17]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Feb 8, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! Master Lu, I have RA. My legs have been unable to walk for several months. Can you please check if the daily recitation I have set for myself is, okay?

Master: Have you been soaking your feet?

Caller: No. Master, what kind of yellow wine are you referring to? I have never used it before.

Master: Yellow wine, any kind of liquor will do. Liquor promotes blood circulation.

Caller: Do I add it while soaking my feet?

Master: Yes, just put some in the water.

Caller: Can I use white liquor instead?

Master: That is fine too, just a little, not too much.

Caller: Soak for half an hour each day?

Master: Yes! At least 20 minutes. While soaking, massage your knee joints with your hands and continuously recite the *Great Compassion Mantra*. You will recover very soon.

(Omitted below)

Q&A 6. RA: No Improvement after Reciting Over 100 Little Houses [18]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on April 28, 2013)

Caller: Hello Master! I am calling on behalf of my elder sister. She has had poor health since childhood, constantly plagued by illnesses. Now she has severe RA. Her joints are already deformed. She has been

reciting Buddhist scriptures and has recited Little Houses for over half a year, but has not felt any improvement.

Master: Her karmic obstacles are this heavy. How many Little Houses has she recited?

Caller: Probably over 100.

Master: What use is just over 100? It is like trying to boil water at home with just a single match. Will the water boil after a while?

Caller: I mainly hoped you could say something to give her a bit of confidence. In our area, not many people believe in Buddhism. She is reciting on her own and lacks a bit of faith.

Master: Her affinity with Buddhism is weak, which is why she is suffering. There is nothing that can be done.

Caller: Then regarding her daily practice...

Master: Basically, the *Great Compassion Mantra*, *Heart Sutra* (心经), and *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Repentance* (礼佛大忏悔文) will be sufficient.

Caller: She recites 49 times each of those daily.

Master: That is okay.

Caller: The *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Repentance* 7 times daily.

Master: Tell her to persist. A match will not boil water, even if you keep lighting one every day. Even if you light 10 boxes of matches, the water still will not boil.

Caller: Okay, I have told her that before, but she might not listen to me. That is why I am asking you.

Master: So many people around the world have improved. How could it be that it does not work for her? Is that possible?

Q&A 7. RA: Significant Improvement after Reciting *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Repentance* 5 Times Daily [19]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Dec. 29, 2013)

Caller: Hello, Master! Last time you told my mother to recite five times the *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Repentance* every day for repenting and eliminating the karma of her RA. She says she feels much better now. Grateful thanks to you, Master!

Master: She should also soak her feet in warm water with yellow wine.

Caller: Got it, Master.

Q&A 8. RA and Paralysis: Caused by Verbal Karma [20]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on August 4, 2018)

Caller: Hello, Master! My mother was born in 1962, the Year of the Tiger. She has been paralyzed for many years due to RA. I would like to ask whether she can stand up again.

Master: Do not rush. Your mother needs to correct a bad habit. Have her recite 86 Little Houses; the spirit will leave. She must stop speaking badly of others. Her verbal karma caused her RA.

Caller: My mother recites every day. She has already recited several hundred Little Houses.

Master: You eat every day too, and you eat for many years, but you still have not grown up? It takes time.

Caller: Understood. We will recite another 86 Little Houses.

Master: Also, tell your mother to fix her bad temper when speaking. In the past, she gossiped a lot and created a lot of verbal karma.

Caller: Got it.

Master: Just reciting Little Houses without fixing the verbal karma is like pouring water into a leaking bucket. It goes in one end and out the other.

Caller: Understood. What else should we do?

Master: Recite scriptures, make vows, and release captive animals. These three are best. If you sincerely want your mother to recover, recite more on her behalf. If you send blessings to your mother every day, she will recover faster.

Caller: That would be a miracle. She has been paralyzed for so many years.

Master: Yes, miracles happen all the time! Many people with cancer who were told by doctors they would not live are still alive today. Some cannot even find the cancer anymore. Do you believe that? Recite diligently and be a good child of Bodhisattva.

Q&A 9. What to Do about RA? [21]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Sept. 7, 2014)

Caller: Hello, Master! The child now has RA. What should we do for RA?

Master: Soak his feet in warm water, and apply warm water or hot towels to the joints. Also, supplement him with calcium.

Caller: Should I give him calcium tablets, or something else?

Master: Give him calcium tablets.

Caller: Master, I usually recite 9 times the *Great Compassion Mantra* for him every day. Is that too few?

Master: That is about right, but you need to recite many Little Houses for him. I am telling you: your child inherited your kind of genetic condition. His mind is confused, and he cannot even speak clearly. Quickly help him by reciting 800 Little Houses for his karmic creditors.

Caller: Okay. Can I recite them in batches of 21 at a time?

Master: Yes.

Caller: Does he need to recite the *Gong De Bao Shan Shen Zhou* (功德宝山神咒)?

Master: No, not necessary.

Caller: So just *Heart Sutra*, *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra*, and five times *Eighty-Eight Buddhas Repentance*, right?

Master: Yes, that will help eliminate karmic obstacles.

Caller: And 49 times each of *Cundi Dharani* (准提神咒), *Mantra to Untie Karmic Knots* (解结咒), and *Xiao Zai Ji Xiang Shen Zhou* (消灾吉祥神咒), right?

Master: That is fine.

Q&A 10. What Causes Arthritis in the Fingers? [22]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Sept. 14, 2018)

Caller: Hello, Master! A female practitioner has arthritis. Her five fingers are becoming increasingly bent, and now her fingers are very painful. The doctor told her to avoid beans. Master, could you sense what she should do?

Master: It is related to eating too many live beings in the past.

Caller: What should she do now?

Master: Recite 108 times the *Amitabha Pure Land Rebirth Mantra* daily.

Q&A 11. The Karmic Cause of severe Arthritis in early Childhood [23]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on August 9, 2020)

Caller: Hello, Master! If a very young child, only about 2-5 years old, develops severe arthritis, what is the karmic cause?

Master: There is definitely a karmic cause from the past life. For children who have arthritis from a young age and weak bones, it is likely due to excessive selfishness in a past life. Because of selfishness, people even use phrases like “selfish to the bone.” So poor bone health is a karmic result of strong selfishness.

Caller: So, it means selfish people in a past life will receive this kind of karmic retribution?

Master: Yes. You can observe whether he grows up to be selfish. You will know.

Caller: If the arthritis disappears as he grows older, does it mean the karma has been resolved?

Master: Yes. If it is gone, then it is gone. If it is no longer there, the karmic result has ended. You may have been a nobleman in a past life, but if you are born into a poor family in this life, then it is gone, it is no longer yours.

(Omitted below)

Q&A 12. How to Pray to Eliminate Karmic Obstacles from RA [24]

(This dialogue took place over the phone on Sept. 14, 2012)

Caller: I have RA and am in pain all day long. Today my left leg hurts, the day after tomorrow it is the right leg. When I pray to Bodhisattva, should I say, “Please help eliminate the karmic obstacle in my left leg” today, and “right leg” tomorrow?

Master: Do not say it that way. Just say, “Please help eliminate the karmic obstacles in my body” and “Please let my body be free from pain.” That is enough.

Caller: Understood. Thank you, Master. Thank you, Guan Yin Bodhisattva.

Master: Goodbye.

Caller: Goodbye.

While the scientific community continues to explore the biological, environmental, and genetic contributors to RA, the root cause remains unidentified, leaving the disease incurable by conventional means. In contrast, the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door offers a distinct perspective: RA is a karmic disease—an affliction stemming from accumulated karmic debts, particularly those associated with taking lives, harmful speech, and unresolved spiritual entanglements. According to the teachings of Master Lu, RA can be reversed by eliminating negative karma through the sincere practice of the Three Golden Buddhist Practices: making great vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, and performing life liberation.

Building upon our previous report [8] and the encouraging outcome noted in Dharma Q&A 7, we propose that RA is a curable condition when approached through these spiritual practices. To further test Master Lu’s theory that RA is caused by karma, we selected four cases in which individuals applied the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door’s Golden Practices, in order to examine whether these methods could indeed lead to complete recovery.

RESULTS

Case 1: After Encountering a Supreme Dharma Door, My Medically Treated 14-Year RA Was Cured in Just Half a Year

With a heart full of immense gratitude, I would like to share with everyone a miraculous experience that happened to me.

I was once a moderate RA patient, with some joint deformities. I had suffered from RA for 14 years. It started in 1999, the year I entered my first year of college. That winter break, I felt sore all over and thought I had caught a bad cold. Living in a rural area, medical care was inconvenient, and I did not go to the hospital. I spent the entire break lying in bed, dazed and unwell. When the new semester began, I found that my joints were swollen and painful, and I could barely get out of bed. Eventually, I was diagnosed with

RA. That marked the beginning of a long and bitter journey of treatment...

During those years, I tried everything: Chinese medicine, Western medicine, acupuncture, herbal baths, and medicinal wines. I was a believer in Buddhism then and often visited temples, but I did not understand how to properly perform daily spiritual practice or recite mantras and sutras. I had read many teachings by virtuous masters online and even encountered certain Dharma doors. But back then, no one guided me to recite Buddhist scriptures correctly to eliminate karma and repay debts. Though I had recited some mantras and sutras, my health never improved.

I was terrified that one day I would end up bedridden like many fellow patients because I saw them paralyzed, in excruciating pain, unable to care for themselves, living lives worse than death. Back then, I never dared to wear short sleeves or shorts in summer. I would wrap myself in thick sweaters and wool pants even on scorching days. My teeth felt icy cold, let alone the rest of my body. At night, I would tightly wrap myself in blankets, afraid even a single arm exposed to air would send a chill deep into my bones.

In November 2013, my husband went to a certain Dharma center to listen to Buddhist teachings and brought back two DVDs. He told me, "Look, Master Lu is amazing." After watching Master Lu's totem readings, I immediately felt that I must start reciting Buddhist scriptures because karma cannot be eliminated otherwise. With the guidance and help of fellow Buddhist practitioners, I gradually entered the practice.

Shortly after I began reciting scriptures, I dreamed of my sister who had passed away eight years ago. I had rarely dreamed of her before. But after starting to recite Little House, she appeared in my dreams. I heard Master Lu's teaching that dreaming of a deceased one means they need to be ascended. I realized how efficacious this Dharma Door was! Thus, I committed to daily recitation, Little Houses, and also regularly participated in life liberation activities with local fellow practitioners.

About half a year into reciting Little Houses, I was washing something in cold water one day. Suddenly, I realized that my body no longer ached. I deliberately went back to the sink to test it again, but still no discomfort. Anyone with RA knows how touching cold water usually worsens joint pain. But I felt nothing. My RA was gone! I was overwhelmed with gratitude. Gratitude to Guan Yin Bodhisattva! Gratitude to Master Lu! Gratitude to fellow practitioners, for your support and help along the way! I cried tears of joy. My arthritis was truly cured!

Those who have not been ill can never truly understand the suffering of the sick. I used to be in such pain that even my fingernails hurt, only my hair was spared. My finger joints were deformed, and my entire body ached. Over more than ten years of seeking treatment, I exhausted all my savings and suffered unimaginable pain. Those years were a living hell.

In recent years, through practicing Buddhism, many of my other chronic conditions have healed without any medication! For example: I had mammary gland hyperplasia and an accessory breast, which required long-term medication. The hospital had scheduled surgery, but after hearing that a high school classmate

did not recover even after surgery, I hesitated and never went. It was not until I started learning Buddhism that I understood how gynecological problems are often related to ignorant acts of abortion. In addition, my long-term pharyngitis, hemorrhoids, and an old ankle injury also healed without medicine. The miraculous effects of this Dharma Door are truly too numerous to count. I am filled with gratitude!

I am truly blessed. Had I not encountered Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door and Master Lu, I cannot imagine what condition I would be in today. After recovering, I sought out former fellow arthritis patients whom I had once treated alongside, hoping to share this precious Dharma with them, to tell them that there is hope! However, many of them had already passed away...

Master Lu enlightens us in *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, Volume 1, Chapter 28: "Everyone will face calamities and suffering. When disasters arrive, it is a sign that our cultivation is maturing. Why? Because only in suffering do people turn to the Buddha and start reciting scriptures. Only through hardship can people be diligent; only through poverty do people strive; only through poor health do people start caring for their bodies. This is the human condition: only when things happen do people consider what to do. Therefore, we must always be prepared for the future."

Master Lu enlightens us in *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, Volume 11, Chapter 20: "If a Buddhist practitioner hasn't tasted the bitterness of life, they will not realize how difficult it is to live in this world. We have suffered countless hardships in this world, some unbearable to even recall. In the midst of right and wrong, we did not know what was true or false and thus committed many unforgivable karmic offenses. We must awaken! We can no longer live in a daze."

Today, I am a disciple of Master Lu. I vow to follow Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu in spreading the Dharma and saving sentient beings throughout this life and all lifetimes to come, never stopping. I will strive to be a Mahayana practitioner, to help countless beings who have an affinity with Buddha, to be a good disciple of Master Lu, and a good child of Guan Yin Bodhisattva. I am working hard to fulfill this vow.

Gratitude to Guan Yin Bodhisattva!

Gratitude to Master Lu!

Gratitude to everyone!

Shared by: M128

Case 2: Miraculous Healing of 21 Years of RA and Disappearance of Multiple Other Illnesses – A Testament to the Efficacy of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door

In September 2014, during the most helpless and painful period of my life, I encountered the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. Today, I am very happy to stand here and share my experience of learning Buddhism. I had suffered from RA for 21 years. During that time, my elder sister accompanied me to numerous hospitals, trying both Chinese and Western medicine, practicing Qigong, and even consulting psychics.

Eventually, at a well-known hospital, I asked the doctor if my condition would ever improve. The doctor replied that it could only be managed with medication. I was heartbroken and burst into tears. With no other option, I had to rely on painkillers prescribed by Western doctors.

RA comes with many complications. Due to long-term medication, I developed osteoporosis. Ten years after the onset of the disease, during a business trip, I slipped into a puddle on the way to the boarding gate with colleagues and fractured my left knee. After surgery, I rested at home for two months, expecting a recovery.

However, a year passed, and instead of healing, the pain worsened. Following the doctor's recommendation, I underwent a second surgery. After that, my left lower leg became bruised and discolored-this bruising remained for years. I also developed a hypersensitive immune system, and my health deteriorated day by day.

By the time I encountered Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door in September 2014, walking had become difficult. When getting on and off buses, I often got caught by the doors due to my slow movement. I moved like an elderly lady. Walking the 100 meters from the bus stop to home often brought tears to my eyes. I had to rest along the way just to make it. My health was declining, and life felt hopeless.

Before learning Buddhism, I did not know that one should avoid psychics. A psychic once told me I might need surgery on both legs by the end of the year, and that I would be bedridden for the rest of my life. I now repent deeply before the Bodhisattvas for my past ignorance.

On September 14, 2014, I discovered Master Jun Hong Lu's blog, including the message board, daily posts, and Q&A sessions. I learned a lot from the experiences shared and understood that listening to recordings and watching Dharma conventions allows one to directly receive the Master's energy and blessings. *Buddhism in Plain Terms* provided essential teachings that helped correct my bad habits. At the same time, I began my daily recitations of Buddhist scriptures.

As I had never studied Buddhism before, reciting mantras and sutras was very difficult at first. But I was inspired by the stories of many elderly fellow practitioners who were illiterate, yet learned each character one by one. Their diligence and perseverance became my role models. I knew my karmic debts were heavy and that I had recited too few scriptures, so I increased the number of daily recitations and prayed to the Bodhisattvas to help me memorize them. Soon, I was able to recite everything through memory fluently. Gratitude to the compassion of the Bodhisattvas.

Initially, I was not planning to attend the Dharma Conference because of other commitments. But the night before, I was restless. I realized Master Lu only came once a year. If I missed it, I would regret it. I made a firm decision to go. Attending the life-changing Dharma Conference, hearing Master's teachings, and watching Master's *Totem Readings* and testimonials from fellow practitioners whose lives had transformed after practicing, made me even more determined to follow the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door.

After the Dharma Conference, I devoted myself to practicing diligently. I no longer played video games or watched TV, which I used to love. I switched to a mostly vegetarian diet and spent all my free time after work on daily recitations and Little Houses. I also read the blog and listened to radio programs daily. Life felt fulfilling and joyful.

Yet, perhaps because of my heavy karmic burden, my body still ached all over. One morning in November, I noticed something strange with my right hand. Since 2013, the muscles in my right hand have atrophied, and except for the thumb, the other four fingers could not move at all. I was referred to orthopedics, then to rehab, then bounced back to orthopedics. Eventually, I gave up seeing doctors.

A psychic had told me I would never recover, so I never imagined that my paralyzed right hand would actually move again! I was overwhelmed with excitement. Through reciting Buddhist scriptures, making vows, and performing life liberation, I truly changed my destiny. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is absolutely real and effective.

Master's radio advice regarding bone and joint issues is soaking feet and taking calcium tablets. I did exactly as instructed. I later dreamed I was happily running, and when I woke up, I was overjoyed! I believed this dream revealed my future: to run and jump freely again.

In December 2014, when I returned to the hospital for a follow-up I felt so much better. I could walk steadily and no longer risked falling. I could even sit and stand without pain.

I wanted to confirm my improvement, and sure enough, the lab reports showed that all inflammation markers had returned to normal. The doctor was shocked and asked me what I had done. I proudly answered, "I recite Buddhist scriptures."

Moreover, my long-standing tinnitus completely vanished, and the bruising on my leg fully disappeared.

I hope my sharing will inspire more people to escape from the torment of illness, change their fate, and join us in this blessed practice. The Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door is true beyond words. Only by experiencing it yourself can you truly understand its power.

With deepest gratitude,

Buddhist Disciple: X129

Case 3: My RA was completely healed via Buddhism

I suffer from severe RA. I have to turn my whole body to look at someone because I cannot turn my neck; my knees cannot bend when I go to the bathroom; I cannot tie my shoelaces, hold onto handlebars while riding a bike, and so on. There are too many inconveniences in life, and I feel powerless. Once, I went to a large hospital for treatment, spending over 20,000 CNY for 4 days and 3 nights. After two visits, I spent over 40,000 CNY, but there was no improvement at all. Over 3 years, I almost depleted all my savings, spending around 200,000 CNY without any results.

Whenever I heard of a place or a method that could treat this disease, I would try it: Chinese and Western

medicines, acupuncture, folk remedies, magnet therapy, infrared treatment, health supplements, and so on. Once, a thought flashed through my mind: after my mother passed away, I wanted to end my life. But for the sake of my mother, to prevent a tragedy from befalling her, I had no way out but to endure it. Knowing my thoughts, my mother, tearfully, said, "With the advancement of medicine nowadays, there will surely be a solution." She tried to comfort me. From then on, every day, I sat in a corner like a guilty child, staring blankly. How to get through the coming days, I have no idea. In the days to come, if there is only expenditure without income, it will be akin to living off one's savings until they are depleted.

Bodhisattva took pity on me. On June 17, 2022, I encountered a noble lady in my life while wearing clothes for healing. Bodhisattva sent her to rescue me, to alleviate my suffering and save me from spending too much money. In this way, I formed an affinity with Buddhism. At that time, a fellow disciple said he (she) had recovered from illness through chanting Buddhist scriptures.

The next day, two more fellow Buddhist disciples came to rescue me, giving me a Buddhist scripture book and teaching me how to recite and pray. They also advised me to listen to the Master's teachings, recordings, totem readings, and practitioners' experiences of practicing Buddhism. They took me to fellow practitioner Z's house to make a vow to be a vegetarian. At first, I dared not make a big vow, only vowing to be vegetarian on the first and fifteenth days of the lunar month. Later, after listening to the Master's teachings, I realized that I must make big vows to eliminate karmic obstacles.

On June 18th, I began reciting Buddhist scriptures. On August 1st, Bodhisattva arranged for me to work at a traditional Chinese medicine clinic, earning 4000 CNY per month and having 4 days off. I never dreamt that in this lifetime, I would still be able to work and earn money.

Later, I made a vow to be vegetarian for life, refrain from killing, and abstain from consuming live sea animals.

One day, when returning, Bodhisattva arranged for me to ride home in a fellow disciple's car. Along the way, upon learning about my RA, she gave me the Great Compassion Dharani Water to drink and offered blessed fruits for me to eat. Tears welled up in my eyes, as I felt utterly incapable of repaying Bodhisattva. I vowed to diligently cultivate myself and help others.

On March 10, 2023, it was the birthday of Guan Yin Bodhisattva. I had a thought in my mind. I wanted to buy some fruits as an offering to Bodhisattva. Suddenly, my wrist joint loosened. Previously, my wrist joint was as tight as a screw, swollen and painful, but now it was loose. In the evening, I asked my fellow practitioner to take the fruits I bought as an offering to Bodhisattva. My joints became even looser as if they were lubricated. Bodhisattva is truly compassionate. That day, I made a vow to recite the *Great Compassion Mantra* 100,000 times over 3 years. Even though I had spent 200,000 CNY without finding a cure, a small act of kindness healed my joints. Therefore, we must cultivate diligently, refrain from wrongdoing, and practice virtuous deeds.

Grateful to Practitioner Z for offering me the Dharma Gems. Without Buddhism, we are nothing. I used to resent my friend for persuading me to buy various things, but these healing clothes were of no use when worn, and the health supplements were consumed in vain. Now, I am grateful to her; she is helping me for my own good. Without these trials and tribulations, I would have missed the opportunity to encounter the Dharma, and I would have suffered throughout my life.

Now, I no longer need injections or medication. What a blessing! If I had not read *Buddhism in Plain Terms* I would still be stubborn, unable to accept any criticism, self-righteous, stingy, lacking compassion, concerned only with myself and disregarding others. I have awakened. That night, I dreamt of pumpkins and loofahs growing in the field without any flaws, just the right size, so beautiful. Grateful for Bodhisattva's encouragement.

A Buddhist practitioner has set up a Buddhist altar at home, and I bought vegetarian food for my fellow practitioners. In the evening, I dreamed of a very large and beautiful red umbrella on the balcony. It was pouring rain outside, but I was inside washing my hands, and only a few drops of rain touched me. I knew Bodhisattva was helping me eliminate my negative karma.

Gratitude to Guan Yin Bodhisattva for allowing me to share how Buddhism healed my RA. With just one thought, Bodhisattva loosened my hands and taught me not to hold onto resentment, and to perceive everything heard and seen as auspicious conditions. Grateful to my fellow practitioners for giving me the opportunity to correct my mistakes, turn over a new leaf, and always think positively. In the evening, I dreamt of numerous golden lotus flowers in the sky. I held one in my hand, radiating golden light. The teachings of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door are true.

Guan Yin Bodhisattva has extended her thousand hands. We must grasp Her hand tightly and strive to become one of the hands and eyes of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, transforming all sentient beings who have an affinity with Buddha. We must recite Buddhist scriptures, practice releasing captive animals, thus transcend the cycle of rebirth for good and attain enlightenment in one lifetime to repay the kindness of the Buddha. Buddhist practitioner: Z130, Gratitude and Namaste!

Case 4: The four golden Buddhist practices cured my 20-plus years of RA

I have revered Guan Yin Bodhisattva since childhood. After getting married, I invited a statue of Guan Yin Bodhisattva into our home, and it has been 25 years now. However, I only offered incense and prostration occasionally, as I did not truly understand how to make offerings properly.

Because I had not yet really encountered the Dharma, I used improper contraception and had several abortions, creating deep karmic debts. At the age of 32, I was diagnosed with RA. My fingers were swollen and stiff, and my legs and feet were in excruciating pain, making everyday life very difficult.

Desperate for a cure, I sought medical help everywhere. As long as I heard about a good Chinese doctor, I would go. Over 20 years, I must have consumed enough Chinese medicine to form a small hill, yet my condition remained unpredictable and hard to control.

Because I lived in a four-story house, just going up and down the stairs became a challenge. Sometimes the pain was so bad that I was afraid to use the stairs at all, and I could no longer make it to the fourth floor to worship the Bodhisattva. I was in pain every day, often in tears, and deeply depressed. Even tiny things could make me lose my temper with my husband and children. My husband said I had changed and lost my gentle nature. The pain and the struggles I suffered were beyond words. At that time, I hoped every day that my children would grow up quickly. I was afraid that when I grew old, I would become a burden to them and lose all confidence in life.

In 2012, a friend took me to a temple to offer incense, and I came to realize how serious the karmic debt of abortion was. I started going to the temple frequently to help ascend those aborted children to a better realm. At that time, I also recited a few Little Houses, but because I had no proper guidance, I eventually gave up. In 2017, I was fortunate to meet a senior Buddhist practitioner, L. She patiently answered all my questions and taught me how to properly worship, recite sutras and mantras, adopt a vegetarian lifestyle, and release captive animals. She also helped interpret my dreams and guided me in making vows and reciting Buddhist scriptures. That same year, she helped me set up a Buddhist altar in my home. I am deeply grateful to practitioner L. If I had not met her, I might still be wandering blindly on the path of practicing Buddhism. On September 19, 2017, the Renunciation Day of Guan Yin Bodhisattva, I knelt before the Bodhisattva and prayed for three things:

1. Cure my RA quickly;
2. My son finds a satisfactory job after graduation;
3. My family becomes healthy and harmonious.

At that time, I was very greedy. One day, I suddenly heard a gentle voice beside my right ear, "Then what about your vow?" I was shocked. Ah! It was a reminder from the Bodhisattva that I must adopt a vegetarian lifestyle. I was seeking so much but had not accumulated enough merits and virtues. To have my prayers answered, I had to make a great vow! I immediately promised Guan Yin Bodhisattva, "I vow to be a vegetarian. I was wrong, and I am sorry for making you worry, Bodhisattva!" As I spoke, I wept uncontrollably. I felt ashamed for being so unenlightened because I had been holding on to five meat meals a month, which was truly ignorant. I am deeply grateful for the compassionate reminder from Guan Yin Bodhisattva!

At the beginning, when I started reciting Little Houses, I was plagued by nightmares. In one, I saw a child covered in leaves and grass, completely naked. I quickly embraced the child and tried to wash him clean. He looked so pitiful! The next morning, I immediately vowed to recite 21 Little Houses in a batch for the

child in my dream and started completing them one batch after another. Sometimes, when I slacked off, I was woken up by a baby's cries. Occasionally, I would be chased by a karmic creditor in a dream. This pushed me to recite Little Houses diligently every day. At the first and the fifteenth of every lunar month, I would release life. Now I have released more than 3,000 fish. I have kept up with daily recitation and read *Buddhism in Plain Terms* in online groups, never slacking. To this day, I have repaid almost 3,000 Little Houses.

While helping the aborted children and other karmic creditors ascend, I began having dreams that offered signs of their successful departure. In one dream, I saw children dressed beautifully, leaving one by one. In another, I watched a doctor make an incision on my hands and feet, pulling out long, dirty strips that resembled pig intestines. In yet another, I pulled a long, dough-like red thread from my mouth that I could have coiled into a heap. I understood these were signs that Guan Yin Bodhisattva was compassionately helping me eliminate my karmic obstacles.

One night, when I got up to use the bathroom, I saw two faint white shadows walk away beside me. After that, my hands and feet felt much lighter. They were no longer bound as if tied down. The two faint white shadows I often saw when I was a feverish child. Another night, I dreamed that Master Lu came to examine my hand and said, "Your hand is fine now." I knew the Little Houses had worked, that the karmic creditor had departed, and the child had been successfully guided to a better realm. I felt overwhelming joy and became more diligent in my practice. I am deeply grateful for the mercy of Guan Yin Bodhisattva and Master Lu!

Today, my RA has been cured. At first, when I began to pray to the Bodhisattva, I had to grit my teeth in pain just to kneel down. Now I walk with ease, can run up and down stairs, wash clothes and cook meals without gloves. My parents, parents-in-law, and husband have witnessed my daily improvements and can rest assured. In the past, I would sleep until noon and still feel exhausted. Now, regardless of how late I work, even until midnight or one or two in the morning, I can get up at eight or nine o'clock and recite Buddhist scriptures. I am energetic every day, full of confidence, and my life is bathed in the light of the Dharma.

In May 2019, I was fortunate enough to attend the Singapore Dharma Conference. Those days felt like living in the heavens, immersed in the joy of the Dharma. After returning, I felt even more confident and diligent, and I recited Little Houses even faster.

Today, I want to tell all those still wandering on the path of learning Buddhism: Trust in Guan Yin Bodhisattva! Master Lu has gifted us such a profound Dharma Door, and the Four Golden Buddhist Practices of making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, releasing life, and reading *Buddhism in Plain Terms* are real, effective, and miraculous beyond words.

Dear fellow practitioners, Guan Yin Bodhisattva is always with us, always caring for us. It is just that we have not practiced well enough or raised ourselves to a higher level of spirituality to be able to sense it. Let us always be diligent, following Master Lu's footsteps with a one-pointed focus, never regressing, and forever propagating the Dharma to help more destined beings overcome suffering and attain happiness!

Buddhist practitioner: Z131

Across four documented cases, patients suffering from RA experienced significant, and in some instances complete, recovery after engaging in the spiritual practices of the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. Case durations ranged from 14 to 21 years of medically treated RA, often accompanied by complications such as joint deformities, immobility, tinnitus, and additional chronic conditions. Despite a lack of relief from conventional therapies, these individuals reported marked improvement or full remission within months of adopting the Three Golden Buddhist Practices: making great vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures (including the Little House), and performing life liberation. Improvements were corroborated by clinical markers in some cases, such as normalization of inflammation indicators. Collectively, these findings support the assertion that RA, traditionally viewed as an incurable chronic disease, may in fact be reversible when approached through karmic purification and diligent spiritual cultivation.

DISCUSSION

RA is generally considered a chronic disease that can accompany patients throughout their lifetime. However, in this study, one patient was cured after 14 years of illness (**Case 1**), and the other two were cured after more than 20 years of suffering (**Cases 3 and 4**). In fact, on Master Lu's blog, there is a case of a woman who suffered from RA for over 40 years and recovered after her daughter recited Little Houses to help her eliminate karmic debts. Therefore, from the Dharma perspective, RA is no longer an incurable chronic disease. It can be cured.

This is similar to other so-called chronic illnesses, such as a 40-year case of eczema [25] or a 50-year case of asthma [26], both of which were healed after practicing the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. This shows that what medical science labels as 'chronic' diseases does not truly reflect their true nature. The medical field has yet to identify the root causes and effective treatments for these conditions, so they are deemed incurable. However, once these illnesses encounter the Dharma, they are no longer chronic and no longer incurable.

What are the true causes of these so-called 'incurable' diseases? Dharma Master Lu has clearly explained this in the Q&A dialogues: karma is the root cause. It is karma that gives rise to these medically incurable illnesses. Medical science has yet to understand the concept of karma, let alone how to treat karmic illnesses. Master Lu has explicitly enlightened us that the karma causing RA includes verbal karma, killing karma, and karma from other sources. Only by controlling the creation of karma can we prevent such illnesses

from arising. This is why the Buddha Dharma guides people to observe precepts and refrain from creating negative karma. This is truly the compassionate, life-saving teaching of the Bodhisattva, a precious remedy for all beings!

The five basic precepts we have discussed earlier form the foundation of moral conduct [7; 27]. Although these are the basic precepts, not everyone can abide by them, and this is why people suffer when karmic retribution arrives.

Our previous research indicated that verbal karma can contribute to recurrent aphthous stomatitis and other oral conditions [28]. This study extends those findings, suggesting that verbal karma may also play a role in RA (Q&A 8). Dharma Master Jun Hong Lu has taught that “those who engage in harsh speech may face the karmic consequence of rebirth in animal realms in future lives [29].” This insight deepens our understanding of the Dharma and underscores the profound benefits of adhering to the precepts. Additionally, killing karma is identified as a significant contributor to RA (Q&A 2, 3) and other intractable diseases [7]. Refraining from killing is crucial for those seeking to prevent RA (Cases 1, 4).

RA, as an autoimmune disease successfully treated through Buddhist practice, is not an isolated example. In fact, we have previously reported similar outcomes in cases of lupus [7], psoriasis [7], chronic urticaria [30], and vitiligo [31], where patients achieved significant recovery through these practices. Together with the RA cases presented in this study and our earlier report [8], these findings suggest that the Golden Buddhist Practices may be effective in facilitating the healing of a range of autoimmune disorders.

Moreover, it is worth emphasizing that autoimmune illnesses are generally chronic conditions, and as stated earlier, the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door has demonstrated its efficacy in managing chronic disease, naturally including autoimmune disease as well.

Although biomedical treatments can alleviate symptoms and slow disease progression, they have yet to fully address the root causes of RA, which remain poorly understood despite extensive investigation. Even with significant efforts devoted to studying the disease’s genetic, environmental, and biological contributors, these approaches primarily focus on symptom management rather than addressing its fundamental origins, making a true breakthrough elusive. We have discussed the limitations of such material-focused inquiries extensively elsewhere and will not elaborate further here [10,32].

There is an anecdote about a patient seeking medical treatment for a chronic disease. Over time, the prolonged use of medications leads to gastrointestinal complications, prompting the addition of treatments for the stomach. As this cycle continues, the patient eventually develops damage to other organs, requiring increasingly complex and extensive medical interventions. Though often recounted with humor, this scenario reflects a common reality in clinical practice and highlights both the limitations of modern medical approaches and the difficult circumstances faced by many patients. It is well-documented that certain medications can cause kidney failure [33] or lead to complications such as osteoporosis (Case 2). While

Western medicine may produce significant side effects, traditional Chinese medicine often fails to offer effective relief even after consuming what is described as a “small hill” of herbs (**Case 4**).

As Buddhist practitioners, we do not oppose the use of medications or medical treatments. Rather, we advocate addressing the root causes of disease. In conjunction with medical treatments that alleviate symptoms, we apply the principles of the Dharma to eliminate the karmic roots of illness, thereby striving to achieve the highest goal: complete recovery.

Some individuals may state that they do not adhere to, or believe in Buddhist teachings, and this is fully acceptable. The tenets of Buddhism do not demand belief or impose acceptance. However, its underlying principles can be viewed as universal laws of cause and effect. According to these teachings, certain actions, such as abortion, may have adverse consequences regardless of belief or skepticism. These effects can manifest as depression [10], autism in offspring [34], oppositional defiant disorder [35] in children, or other undesirable outcomes [7]. This is akin to medical or biological phenomena: regardless of whether one believes in medical science, consuming contaminated food can lead to gastrointestinal illness. In both contexts, belief or disbelief does not affect the outcome.

We recommend that medical professionals consider gaining an understanding of Buddhist teachings, particularly the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. This could enable them to offer patients with RA an additional pathway to address the root causes of their condition and ultimately achieve more comprehensive and lasting relief.

CONCLUSION

RA has long been classified as an incurable chronic disease within the framework of modern medicine, with its pathogenesis attributed to a complex interplay of genetic, biological, and environmental factors. However, the cases presented in this study provide compelling evidence that RA may be reversible through Dharma practices and the resolution of karmic debts. By sincerely applying the Five Golden Buddhist Practices taught by the Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door, making vows, reciting Buddhist scriptures, releasing captive animals, sincerely repenting past wrongdoings and refraining from repeating them, and studying *Buddhism in Plain Terms*, patients with long-standing RA refractory to medical treatments have demonstrated significant clinical recovery. These findings challenge conventional assumptions and underscore the potential role of karmic causes and Dharma practice in the management of chronic illness.

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ETHICAL STATEMENT

The author did not involve any part of the experimental design, experimental treatments and result analysis of the patients. All the experimental procedures and practices by the presenters were done by themselves independently.

STATEMENT BY TRANSLATOR AND WRITER

The 12 Q&As and 4 stories in the text were translated from Chinese to English based on their intended meaning rather than a word-for-word approach. The remaining portions of the paper were written based on my limited understanding of Guan Yin Citta Dharma Door. If there are any inaccuracies or deviations from the true meaning of the Chinese version, or if the content does not accurately reflect Master Lu's teachings, I sincerely seek forgiveness from the Greatly Merciful and Greatly Compassionate Guan Yin Bodhisattva, all Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, Dharma Protectors, and Master Jun Hong Lu.

DISCLAIMER OF LIABILITY

The contents of the presentation, comments, and discussion, including text, images, and other information obtained from Dharma practitioners, are provided strictly for reference purposes. Due to the unique nature of individual karma, results similar to those experienced by the practitioner may not be replicated. The experiences and advice shared should not be construed as medical advice or a diagnosis.

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